

Candida rugosa lipase bio-conjugation to cellulose nanocrystals with high immobilization efficiency

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ABSTRACT. Nanostructured materials represent promising substrates for biocatalyst immobilization and activation. In this work, we demonstrate a green and sustainable approach to enzyme immobilization using cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) derived from renewable sources. Compared to conventional supports, CNCs offer biodegradability, low toxicity, and high surface area, enabling efficient and eco-friendly immobilization of *Candida rugosa* lipase (*CRL*). Covalent bio-conjugation to TEMPO-oxidized CNCs achieves high immobilization efficiency without toxic by-products, aligning with green chemistry principles and offering a scalable route for sustainable biocatalysis. The immobilization reaction of the biocatalyst on the biodegradable substrates retains the activity of the enzyme. Several characterization methods, including Attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR), high-resolution synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD), Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), bicinchoninic acid assay (BCA), solid state NMR (ssNMR) and enzyme activity analyses, were employed to evaluate the structural, morphological, and functional properties of the immobilized biocatalysts. In particular, ssNMR demonstrates the highest immobilization efficiency achieved through the covalent immobilization. This reveals the potential of TO_CNCs for quantitative immobilization of enzymatic units, avoiding dispersion of the precious biocatalysts.

1. Introduction

Enzymes represent the most used green catalysts in preparative academic and industrial chemistry, as they require mild working conditions and empower the synthesis of high added-value chemicals and products of pharmaceutical interest.^{1,2} Moreover, their immobilization makes possible recyclability and ease of manipulation and is compatible with an industrial application. Common immobilization strategies include non-covalent/non-specific adsorption, covalent bonding (bio-conjugation), entrapment in a gel or in a polymeric nanocapsule or cross-linking to produce cross-linked enzyme aggregates (CLEA).³

Nanostructured materials present some advantages as immobilization substrates, since they possess a high surface-to-volume ratio, allowing high catalyst loading and lower costs for industrial biotechnology. So far, enzymes immobilized on nanoparticles have shown a broader working pH and temperature range than the native enzymes. In some cases, enhancement of biocatalytic activity was observed together with the above-described advantages. Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.

A further development consists in the immobilization of enzymes on cheap and biodegradable nanocelluloses, which potentially enhances sustainability for industrial applications.⁵ Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs)⁶ are elementary fibrils with widths of 5-50 nm and lengths between 100 nm and 500 nm. They can be isolated in the laboratory by acid hydrolysis, as early reported by Rånby⁷ and by Battista et al.,⁸ starting from pre-purified cellulose sources. CNCs possess high crystallinity, low density (1.6 g×cm³) and high tensile strength (Young's modulus 100–140 GPa). Furthermore, CNCs toxicity for the environment and for living cells and organisms has already been ruled out by several studies.^{9,10,11}

So far, literature has reported the immobilization of enzymes such as papain,¹² lipase,^{13,14} penicillin acylase,¹⁵ galactosidase,¹⁶ cyclodextrineglycosyl transferase (CGT-ase),¹⁷ glucose oxidase,¹⁸ peroxidase,¹⁹ laccase²⁰ and lysozyme Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. on cellulose nanocrystals or cellulose nanofibers with interesting results. The leitmotif of the previously described research was the achievement of stable immobilized and recyclable biocatalysts. Effortless recyclability was enabled by magnetic cellulose nanocrystals, that could be recovered exploiting their magnetic properties,^{12,13,15} while the biocatalyst stabilization could be achieved by glutaraldehyde Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. cross-linking,^{13,15} enzyme direct bio-conjugation with the nanocelluloses^{14,19,21} or nanoparticle binding mediators.^{17,18,20} However, our previous work has shown that the surface chemistry of CNCs directly

affects the number of immobilized enzymatic units, in spite of the potentialities offered by the high specific surface area of the nanostructured material.^{Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.}

In this study, we demonstrate the enhanced sustainability of biocatalyst immobilization on cellulose nanocrystals, with outcomes influenced by their surface chemistry. Our approach achieves high immobilization efficiency through covalent bonding, to effectively mitigate the issue of enzyme leakage from the support reported in other studies. Additionally, the immobilization reaction is carried out with chemicals producing byproducts with lower toxicity than other reference cross-linking compounds as glutaraldehyde; the biocatalytic system is used in water, and the biodegradable support further contributes to the overall eco-friendly profile of the system. Moving in this direction, in the present work we selected lipase as a model enzyme for immobilisation on CNCs. Extracellular lipases (EC 3.1.1.3) produced by microorganisms are widely studied due to their numerous applications in various biotechnological processes,²³ and their recent demonstrated attitude to catalyze even esterification reactions in water.^{Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} Our approach applied to lipases could solve main issues, like the requirement of an organic environment to swell the inert lipase immobilization support,^{Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.,²⁶} and leakage of biocatalyst during repetitive uses, especially occurring in water with nonspecifically immobilized systems.^{27,28}

Our approach leverages CNCs derived renewable cellulose sources, and avoids the use of synthetic polymers or non-biodegradable carriers, to obtain a recyclable immobilized system ideal for use in water environment.

In detail, we set out to compare the efficiency of nonspecific and covalent immobilization approaches, along with the application of functional and spectroscopic assays to reveal the structural consequences of the applied immobilization strategy. In detail, sulfated cellulose nanocrystals (S_CNCs), widely considered as benchmark for cellulose nanocrystals, were used as nonspecific substrate for *CRL* immobilization at pH 7.0. Furthermore, bio-conjugation to TEMPO-oxidised cellulose nanocrystals (TO_CNCs) was accomplished to outperform the results of nonspecific immobilization. We combined infrared (IR) and solid-state NMR (ssNMR) spectroscopies, as spectroscopic methods applicable to our solid preparations. 1D and 2D magic-angle-spinning (MAS) ssNMR was used for its proven track record in the analysis of cellulose nanocrystals and immobilized proteins alike.^{29,30,Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} Moreover, we used ¹H MAS NMR to probe the potential role of hydration waters in the process.

³² The isolated lipase/CNCs biocatalysts displayed preserved activity, as determined in *p*-nitrophenyl laurate (*p*NPL) hydrolytic tests but significantly differed for the lipase immobilization yield.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Preparation of sulfated and TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanocrystals

Sulfated cellulose nanocrystals (S_CNCs) were prepared from Avicel by sulfuric acid hydrolysis (using H₂SO₄ aq 64%), according to our published procedures.^{33,34,35} During the reaction, sulfuric acid not only catalyzes the hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds at the amorphous cellulose phase, but randomly esterifies the pending primary alcohol functions of cellulose. This results in cellulose nanocrystals presenting surface sulfate groups and negative charges.³⁶ TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanocrystals (TO_CNCs), which possess surface carboxyl groups, were obtained from unfunctionalized cellulose nanocrystals (N_CNCs), prepared from Avicel by HCl hydrolysis,³⁵ followed by oxidation in the presence of sodium hypochlorite, sodium bromide and 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine 1-oxyl radical (TEMPO radical).^{Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} This reaction turns surface primary alcohol functions of nanocellulose into carboxylate groups. TO_CNCs were purified by dialysis with deionized water and isolated in 89% yield. A conductimetric titration of TO_CNCs revealed a degree of oxidation (DO) of 0.099 (Equation S1), which means that ~10% of the total glucopyranose rings were accessible to the oxidizing reagents.

2.2 XRD characterization

Figure 1. Diffractogram of S_CNC (in blue), TO-CNCs (in grey).

Figure 1 displays the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the three samples, all of which exhibit characteristic diffraction peaks corresponding to cellulose I, the native crystalline form of cellulose present in plant biomass. The XRD profiles are plotted as a function of the absolute momentum transfer (Q). Crystallinity indices (CI) were calculated using the Segal method,³⁸ defined as $CI = (I_{200} - I_{am})/I_{200}$, where I_{200} represents the maximum intensity of the (200) reflection (centered at 1.6Q in the present spectra, equivalent to 22.6° in 2θ using $CuK\alpha_1$ radiation), and I_{am} corresponds to the intensity of the amorphous cellulose at 1.3Q. The S-CNC sample exhibits the highest crystallinity index of 80.0%, highlighting the efficacy of sulfuric acid treatment in selectively hydrolyzing amorphous cellulose regions. In comparison, TO-CNCs show a CI of 70.0%, consistent with values subsequently confirmed by solid-state NMR measurements.

2.2 CRL characterization

Research highlights *C. rugosa* as one of the most extensively examined microorganism for lipase production. As a non-sporulating, pseudofilamentous, unicellular, and non-pathogenic yeast (also known as *Candida cylindracea*), *C. rugosa* produces a mixture of lipases known for their optical purity and specificity in hydrolyzing and synthesizing valuable compounds. In recent years, this capability has been used to develop carbohydrate esters and amino acid derivatives,^{39,40} and to enable biodegradation of polymers.⁴¹ To offset its rising cost, CRL is often used in immobilized forms, entrapped in durable, low-cost supports that extend its lifespan.⁴² We preliminarily analysed CRL (average molecular weight 67000 Da) purity through SDS PAGE (Figure S1).^{43,44} Before performing the immobilization on cellulose nanocrystals, we also assessed its activity by a kinetic assay.^{45,46,47} This method is a kinetic/colorimetric assay, which is conducted using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, as described by Shirai and Jackson.^{Errorre. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} Lipase activity is measured using an ester of *p*-nitrophenol with an aliphatic carboxylic acid as substrate, chosen as *p*-nitrophenyl laurate (*pNPL*) in our experiments. The reaction releases *p*-nitrophenol, which produces an absorption band at 400 nm and a yellow coloration. One enzyme unit U is defined as the amount of enzyme that releases 1.0 nanomole of *p*-nitrophenol per minute. ^{Errorre. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.,Errorre. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} We performed the kinetic experiments in a 100 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 and room temperature, determining an activity of 26 enzymatic units per mg of lyophilized protein, in line with the theoretical enzymatic activity declared by the provider. (Figure S3)

2.3 Immobilization experiments

The non-specific self-assembly between *CRL* and S_CNCs (Figure 2a) was performed by simply incubating their solutions in a 100 mM phosphate buffer pH 7.0 at 10:1 weight ratio, respectively. The use of pH 7.0 allows the electrostatic interaction between the sulfate groups on the S_CNCs nanocrystals and the protein's lysine residues, which carry a positive charge, to be exploited for self-assembly. This pH falls within the stability range for *CRL* (Figure S6). Then, the aggregates were purified and redispersed for subsequent characterization. The pH 7.0 yielded the most satisfactory results, even if above the protein isoelectric point (pI 4.2). Even if the enzyme positive charge would be maximized at $\text{pH} < \text{pI}$, any attempt to perform immobilization experiments at pH 4 or 5 resulted in lower immobilization yield as a consequence of the enzyme's lower stability in acidic conditions (Figure S6). To maximize the protein loading for increasing solid-state NMR sensitivity, the immobilization at pH 7 was also repeated by mixing S_CNCs and *CRL* in a 4:1 weight ratio (as discussed later in the NMR characterization paragraph).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of a) immobilization of *CRL* on sulfated nanocrystals (S_CNCs), and b) TEMPO-mediated oxidation of N_CNCs to carboxylated nanocrystals (TO_CNCs), and subsequent bio-conjugation to *CRL*. For the bio-conjugation of *CRL* to TO_CNCs, a covalent reaction between the -COOH groups present in TO_CNCs and -NH_2 groups of lysine residues of *CRL* was carried out using EDC (1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide) and N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) in deionized water (Figure 2b). TO_CNCs were mixed with lipase in a 2:1 weight ratio to maximize protein loading. The isolation of the biohybrid system followed the same protocol as in the earlier case.

The bicinchoninic acid (BCA) test was performed on the supernatant solutions and on the immobilized systems dispersions to quantify the protein and the nanocrystals. A calibration curve ($y=0.0048x+0.0549$, r^2 0.980, RSD%=0.9 %) was obtained using lipase as the reference standard (working range 0–60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, LOQ, quantification limit, 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and was used to extrapolate the unknown concentration of the *CRL* immobilized on S_CNC and TO-CNC. A reference containing CNCs was used to subtract from the measured absorbances the interference generated by the scattering of nanocrystals and their interaction with the test reagents through their available reducing termini. *Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.* The results, reported in Table 1, show that about 38 μg were immobilized on 1 mg of recovered S_CNCs (RSD% 15%, enzyme immobilization yield 7.2%). Vice versa, immobilization on TO_CNCs, gave 74 μg per mg of nanocrystals (RSD% 5%, enzyme immobilization yield 23.4%) meaning a three-fold higher number of immobilized enzymatic units in the covalently immobilized system. This indicates that electrostatic interactions alone are not efficient in ensuring a reasonable anchoring yield. The BCA test was useful to have a first evaluation of the efficiency of the two immobilization approaches, clearly pointing at the superior efficacy of the covalent immobilization against the nonspecific interaction.

Table 1. Concentration of *CRL* extrapolated by BCA in the bioconjugates with nanocrystals.

Sample	Immobilized enzyme (<i>CRL</i>) [$\mu\text{g}_{\text{CRL}}/\mu_{\text{tot}}$] $\times 100$	Immobilized enzyme (<i>CRL</i>) [$\mu\text{g}_{\text{CRL}}/\mu_{\text{cnc}}$]
S_CNCs: <i>CRL</i> ^a	7.2	38
TO_CNC@ <i>CRL</i> ^b	23.4	74

^a *CRL* and S_CNCs were mixed in 1:10 weight ratio. ^b *CRL* and TO_CNCs were mixed in 1:2 weight ratio.

The successful immobilization was proven by the attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FT-IR) spectra. Figure 3 shows the spectra collected on dry samples of: lyophilized lipase, dried S_CNCs and dried self-assembled S_CNCs:*CRL*, dried TO_CNCs and TO_CNCs@*CRL*. The spectrum of the S_CNCs displayed the common features of cellulose I, with a strong absorption band at 3325 cm^{-1}

¹ attributed to -OH groups stretching forming intramolecular hydrogen bonds. This peak appeared with a shoulder at approximately 3300 cm⁻¹ which was also found in the composite S_CNCs:CRL. On the contrary, in this region the lipase protein presented a very broad absorption peak centred at lower energies (3234 cm⁻¹) resulting from the stretching of N-H bonds. This absorption produced, in the nanocellulose-protein composites, an apparent broadening of the O-H stretching peak at lower energies. Absorption bands attributed to C-H stretching modes below 3000 cm⁻¹ were also clearly visible in the nanocelluloses at 2895 cm⁻¹. More structured bands were present in lipase, with additional peaks at 2948 and 2864 cm⁻¹. These peaks could be found as well in the S_CNCs:CRL composite (Please compare the ESI, Figure S3). The signal centred at 1646 cm⁻¹ in S_CNCs might be attributed to bending of water contained in the cellulose nanocrystals. In this region, lipase presented the amide I (1655 cm⁻¹) and amide II (1510 cm⁻¹) bands, but apparently, only the amide I band was preserved in the hybrid system. A similar behaviour was observed also by other authors with the lipase from *Candida Antarctica*.¹³ The intense band between 913 and 1220 cm⁻¹ in S_CNCs originated from stretching modes of single C-O-C bonds of the acetal units. In this region, the S_CNCs:CRL hybrid structure presented an increase in the signal intensity, together with the appearance of an extra signal centred at 850 cm⁻¹ originating from lipase and attributed to N-H bonds wagging.

Figure 3. ATR-FTIR spectra of light grey TO:CNC@CRL; grey TO_CNCs; red CRL; green S_CNC:CRL; blue S_CNCs.

At 3350 cm^{-1} the signals due to OH stretching are observed in the spectra of TO_CNCs and of their bio-conjugate with lipase. Furthermore, the carboxyl group stretching peak at 1720 cm^{-1} almost disappears in the bio-conjugated system TO-CNCs@CRL. Here, a new signal, red-shifted to lower energies compared to the starting TO_CNCs, appears, indicating both the formation of amide bonds between the carboxyl groups of cellulose nanocrystals and the lysines of lipase. This suggests that the immobilization process was effective.

Figure 4 shows the kinetics of hydrolysis of *pNPL* with the two immobilized systems (after the first 50 seconds of reaction because this is the time required for immobilized lipase to activate, compare Figure S4 in the supplementary). The optical density increases over time, reflecting the production of *p*-nitrophenol. Thanks to these measurements, it was possible to calculate the enzymatic units with equations S2-3, obtaining a value of 48 U/mg_{CRL} for the S_CNCs:CRL system. This value, of the same order of magnitude of the one found for free CRL, is compatible with a highly mobile protein, which can re-orient on the surface of the nanocrystals. The apparent increased activity could be even attributed to protein purification during the manipulation of the assemblage (i.e. immobilization of the most active isozymes of lipase).

Figure 4. *p*-nitrophenyl laurate kinetic test on the immobilized systems: blue line, blank recorded with CNCs alone; green line, S_CNCs:CRL; grey line, TO_CNC@CRL.

The S_CNCs:CRL system shows a steeper slope than the other sample, suggesting faster product formation and greater enzyme-substrate (p NPL) interaction. Conversely, the calculated activity value in the case of immobilized TO_CNC@CRL was 0.8 U/mg_{CRL}. This value confirms the covalently immobilized nature of the sample. The reduced enzymatic activity can be explained as an effect of the structural rigidification of lipase due to the formation of multiple covalent linkages.^{Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} This structural rigidification is almost absent in the nonspecific sample, in which the protein can more easily reorganise once in contact with the substrate. Nevertheless, the covalent immobilization of CRL on TO-nanocrystals still has the distinctive advantage that the immobilization quantity of protein is higher (compare ssNMR and BCA results), enabling higher economic value for application purposes and more sensitive structural characterizations by ssNMR techniques in this work.

2.4 Morphology of the immobilized systems

The morphology of nanocellulose and lipase immobilized on nanocellulose samples was evaluated by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). The relevant micrographs are reported in Figure 5.

It is evident from the micrograph that the S_CNC nanocrystals show a tendency to form small aggregates which bundle together from the long side (Figure 5a). The immobilized sample S_CNC:CRL continues to show the presence of the nanocrystals. However, their behavior is changed: in fact, the tendency to aggregate is increased and small spherical aggregates, probably from lipase (evidenced by green circles in Figure 5b), are also present in the film. The S_CNC:CRL morphology shows recognizable nanocrystals but scarce features attributable to the protein, pointing to a very low amount of immobilized CRL.

Neutral nanocrystals, precursors of TO_CNCs, show similar shape to S_CNCs, which should relate rather to the cellulose source (namely Avicel) than the acid used for digestion (HCl_{aq} vs H₂SO_{4, aq}). The TO-CNC@CRL morphology (Figure 5d) resembles the morphology of a similar covalently assembled system, composed of TO_CNCs and lysozyme from chicken egg white,²¹ presenting a large aggregate, with dimensions in the order of microns, composed of cellulose nanocrystals embedded in a protein matrix, and an area (at the bottom of the micrograph, evidenced by a yellow circle) where individual nanocrystals and self-assembled protein units are clearly identified.

Figure 5. FE-SEM of (a) S_CNC; (b) S_CNC:CRL; c) CNCs obtained from Avicel by HCl hydrolysis; (d) TO_CNC@CRL. All samples were deposited from a 0.5 mg/L suspension in water on silicon. The analysis was performed on the samples without necessity of a coating layer.

2.5 NMR studies on the immobilized systems

Next, we used solid-state (ssNMR) to gain structural/dynamical insights into the impact of protein immobilization on the CNCs and estimates of the extent of modification. Here we take advantage of the well-known capabilities for magic angle spinning (MAS) ssNMR to probe immobilized or aggregated proteins, as well as polysaccharides such as cellulose. First, MAS NMR samples holders (known as MAS rotors) were packed with known sample amounts of dry lipase (11 mg) and S_CNC (16 mg), as reference samples. For these ^{13}C -detected measurements, we deployed cross polarization (CP). The CP ssNMR experiment transfers polarization from more sensitive nuclei (e.g., ^1H) to less sensitive nuclei (e.g., ^{13}C) which greatly improves sensitivity. Whilst CP spectra are sensitive to dynamics,^{Errorre. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} dry sample conditions may enable their use in a semi-quantitative way, as for this case to obtain an estimation of the fraction of the protein bound to cellulose (i.e., the mass percentage of protein relative to cellulose mass).

Relevant 1D ^{13}C CP spectra are reported in Figure 5a. The cellulose-containing samples exhibited similar spectral profiles, reflecting the dominant cellulose signals. Among the cellulose peaks, the C4 carbon peaks indicated a substantial crystalline content, approximately 60%, as determined by the integration of the two C4 peaks.^{54,55}Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. This is consistent with the typical crystallinity of CNCs. A comparison between the lipase and S_CNC spectra shows that the peak at 91 ppm belonging to cellulose does not overlap with peaks from the protein. Conversely, protein peaks between 15 and 50 ppm, attributed to C α and C β carbons, do not overlap with cellulose peaks.⁵⁷ Thus, the ratio between the area of the peak corresponding to the crystalline C4 carbon of cellulose (at 91 ppm) and the area of the protein region (between 15 and 50 ppm) allowed an estimate of the degree of protein immobilization on the CNCs in S_CNC:CRL. Therefore, S_CNC:CRL was measured and analysed, using the sample in which lipase was mixed with CNCs at 25% wt ratio. This choice was necessary because the 10% ratio experiments yielded a sample lacking the necessary spectral sensitivity. An apparent protein binding efficiency of roughly 3 wt%, corresponding to ~ 30 μg of protein per mg of nanocellulose, based on the above-mentioned spectral analysis was calculated. Thus, these analyses consistently report a modification level near 3 wt-%, which is lower than the employed protein amounts used to prepare the sample (25 wt%). This points at a limit of the noncovalent immobilization approach, where a 12% immobilization yield can be reached dramatically increasing the amount of protein mixed to the nanocrystals.

Next, in Figure 6, the ssNMR characterisation of TO_CNCs and TO_CNCs@CRL is reported. 1D ^{13}C CP MAS NMR spectra are reported in Figure 6a. A signal at ~ 175 ppm was observed in the spectrum of TEMPO-oxidised CNCs, corresponding to carboxylic groups on the cellulose surface. The same 175 ppm peak appeared relatively broader in the case of the protein-immobilised sample, having in this case an additional contribution from the protein acyl groups. The TO_CNCs@CRL sample showed a greater extent of protein binding compared to the S_CNCs, approximately 30 wt%, calculated using the same method described above. Considering that TO_CNCs and CRL were mixed for this immobilization experiment in a 2:1 weight ratio, this estimation would indicate a much more effective and near-quantitative immobilization yield for the covalent approach, compared to the above procedures. An increase in immobilization efficiency was also noted from the BCA test (7.2% immobilization yield for S_CNC:CRL, while 23.4% for TO_CNC:CRL), even if this colorimetric assay is affected by several

interferences, including the scattering produced in the dispersed samples by the nanocrystals, that could account for the discrepancies found among the two techniques.

Figure 6. a) ^{13}C CP MAS NMR spectra recorded on lipase, *CRL* immobilised on *S_CNCs* and *S_CNCs*. Boxed regions indicate peaks from CNC C4 (near 91 ppm) and spectral regions specific to protein (near 10-50 ppm).; b) ^1H MAS NMR spectra recorded on *CRL* immobilised on *S_CNCs* and *S_CNCs*; c) ^1H T_1 values of *S_CNCs* and *CRL* immobilised on *S_CNCs* obtained through ^1H detection.

Figure 7. a) ^{13}C CP MAS NMR spectra recorded on TEMPO-oxidised CNCs and lipase covalently bound to TEMPO-oxidised CNCs; b) ^1H MAS NMR spectra recorded on the same samples; c) 2D ^{13}C - ^1H CP-based HETCOR MAS NMR spectra without and with ^1H - ^1H spin diffusion of 10 ms. The introduction of spin diffusion allows for the observation of additional peaks at around 5.4 ppm (indicated by the dashed line in the figure) deriving from water-cellulose interaction.

For a further inspection of these samples, we performed also 2D ^{13}C - ^1H CP-based HETCOR MAS NMR spectra. The 2D HETCOR spectrum (Figure 6d; left) allow the assignment of the proton chemical shifts in cellulose, as expected and previously reported. The lower sensitivity of the 2D spectrum did not permit the observation of protein ^{13}C signals. Next, we introduced in the 2D experiments a ^1H - ^1H spin diffusion time that enables longer-range (^1H) polarization exchange between different molecular species. A series of additional peaks at around 5.4 ppm (^1H frequency) were observed, which we attribute to water-cellulose interactions. The atypical ^1H shift (expected at 4.8 ppm) is consistent with prior studies of hydration waters bound to polysaccharides.³² Surprisingly, these water-cellulose peaks were relatively intense in TO_CNCs compared to TO_CNCs@CRL, where they appeared almost absent. We propose that these findings may be explained by the protein modifications displacing water molecules normally present on the cellulose surface.

To further investigate the modifications and hydration in these samples by MAS NMR, we turned to ^1H NMR experiments on these same samples (Figure 5b; 6b). Note that this experiment detects all protons in the sample, including not only cellulose but also protein and water hydrogens, potentially without the resolution to distinguish them reliably. ^1H spectra showed a narrower line for S_CNCs:CRL relative to pure S_CNCs (Figure 4b). This suggested the presence of increased water content in the immobilised sample. Interestingly, an opposite trend was observed for TO_CNCs : the TO_CNCs sample exhibited a narrower lineshape than TO_CNCs@CRL , suggesting decreased water content in the protein-bound sample.

These data pointed to a potentially interesting difference in the dynamics and/or hydration of these samples. We determined therefore also the ^1H longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) values for both S_CNCs and lipase-immobilized S_CNCs by combining a DUMBO sequence (used for ^1H homonuclear decoupling)⁵⁸ with the classical saturation recovery experiment. Two distinct T_1 values were observed: 0.18 s for S_CNCs and 1.6 s for lipase-immobilized S_CNCs , the latter approximately one order of magnitude larger (Figure 5c). The increased T_1 value for the S_CNCs:CRL offers further support for a higher water content compared to pure S_CNCs , since the two samples have similar crystallinity/molecular order, as evidenced by the ^{13}C 1D spectra.

In summary, the ssNMR points to interesting differences in the presence of water in the case of lipase immobilized on S_CNCs and TO_CNCs . We speculate that for the former the hydration waters are essential for mediating electrostatic interactions between the positively charged protein residues and the negatively charged sulfate groups on the cellulose surface (this is reasonable, because, as can be demonstrated by elemental analyses, sulfate groups in S_CNCs have H_3O^+ as counterion).³⁴ In the latter samples, the formation of covalent amide bonds between the cellulose carboxylic groups and the protein primary amine groups may be accompanied by water displacement. This may be related to the activation reaction involving carboxyl groups through NHS/EDC chemistry which expels water in the form of an urea derivative. This result supports a more intimate contact between the surface of the nanocrystals and the protein in the TO_CNCs@CRL sample. Water displacement seems therefore related to the structural rigidification of the protein induced by the covalent bonding and causing its drop of enzymatic activity per mg of pure enzyme. It may be that these differences in dynamics and hydration underpin the observed differences in enzyme activity as observed above.

2.6 Further considerations

To clearly highlight the advantages of the immobilization approach presented in this work, a comparison with previously reported *CRL* immobilization strategies is presented in Table 2. The main parameters considered include the chemical nature of the support, the immobilization efficiency, the solvent required for biocatalyst use, operational stability, and the biodegradability, if discussed in the reference literature.

Table 2. *CRL* immobilization strategies: comparison with this work

Support	Source	Enzyme loading [mg _{enzyme} /g _{support}]	Solvent ^a	Recyclability	Biodegradability	Ref
Celite	Mineral (non-renewable)	6.6	Water/acetone, octane	Few cycles	NO	26
PHB^b	Renewable (bacterial origin)	NA	Organic	Moderate	YES	59
PS-DVB^c	Synthetic (non renewable)	NA	Hexane, octane, acetone	High (multiple cycles)	NO, microplastic source	60
This work	Renewable (plant based)	74 (BCA) ~330 (30% w/w, ssNMR)	Water	High potential	Potential	

^a The column specifies the solvent used for the biocatalysis, not the immobilization. ^b PHVB = poly(hydroxybutyrate). ^c PS-DVB = poly(styrene-co-divinylbenzene)

As shown in Table 2, traditional supports such as Celite, although widely used, present limitations including low enzyme loading and the need for organic solvents like acetone to prevent enzyme solubilization—posing challenges for scalability and environmental safety. Synthetic supports such as PS-DVB offer high recyclability but are derived from non-renewable sources and contribute to microplastic pollution. PHVB, while biodegradable and renewable, requires organic solvents and shows only moderate recyclability.

In contrast, the strategy developed in this work utilizes a renewable, plant-based support—cellulose nanocrystals—with significantly higher enzyme loading (up to ~330 mg enzyme/g support as estimated by ssNMR), covalent immobilization that minimizes enzyme leakage, and water as the reaction medium. This not only enhances operational stability but also reduces the toxicity associated with the immobilization process, as it avoids the use of glutaraldehyde and instead employs EDC/NHS, whose decomposition products are less harmful. Furthermore, the support is biodegradable, aligning with green chemistry principles.

A final node to be solved remains concerning the procedures that can be used to prepare the cellulose nanocrystals. Acid hydrolysis, often used as an effective method to achieve the formation of nanocrystals in moderate yields, releases waste containing concentrated acids, basically against the green chemistry principles. The recent literature has highlighted that the sustainability of the production of cellulose nanocrystals could be improved synthesizing the nanocellulose by mechano-enzymatic approach.^{34, Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.} This approach could be applied in the future to synthesize enzymatic N_CNCs that can then be converted into TO_CNCs.²¹

3. Conclusion

Immobilization experiments of *Candida rugosa* lipase on sulfated and TEMPO-oxidised cellulose nanocrystals revealed interactions that regulate the activity of the enzyme. Nonspecific immobilization demonstrated higher enzymatic activity of the immobilized protein, due to a more mobile enzyme interacting with the surface of the cellulose nanocrystals. However, the amount of immobilized protein was in this case very low (<10%). The covalent binding of the *CRL* to TO_CNCs maximized the immobilization yield, which in turn enabled significant results via ssNMR analysis, even with lower activity per mg of immobilized protein (0.8 U/mg_{CRL}). Even if displaying a slower activity, the immobilization of protein, assessed by ssNMR, was almost quantitative with the covalent approach, pointing at an economic convenience of the bio-conjugation against nonspecific immobilization. The higher bio-conjugation efficiency highlights its potential for biocatalysis and applications requiring prolonged stability of the enzyme. Despite a reduction in enzymatic activity due to structural rigidification, the covalent immobilization of *CRL* on CNCs offers a sustainable and efficient platform for biocatalysis. The use of biodegradable, renewable nanocellulose supports and aqueous-phase conjugation chemistry aligns with the principles of green chemistry. This work demonstrates a significant

green advance over conventional immobilization strategies, paving the way for environmentally friendly and economically viable enzyme-based technologies. Solid-state NMR and SEM provided molecular and structural evidence of successful immobilization, revealing changes in morphology, water interactions and cellulose dynamics. The observed water displacement and decrease in cellulose mobility following *CRL* covalent immobilization underscore the intimate interaction between the protein and the nanocellulose matrix. More in detail, water displacement seems to contribute to the protein structural rigidification induced by the covalent bond with the nanocellulose. Continued optimization of immobilization techniques and further elucidation of enzyme-nanocellulose interactions could pave the way for new biohybrid materials with advanced functionality.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Full experimental procedures, additional plots and diagrams cited in the main text. All this data is included in the Supporting Information of this article. Datasets are available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CRL, *Candida rugosa* lipase; *S_CNC*, sulfated cellulose nanocrystals; *TO_CNC*, TEMPO-oxidised cellulose nanocrystals; *pNPL*, *p*-nitrophenyl laurate.

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